

HuBERT Ensemble Models for Singing Voice Deepfake Detection

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Abstract

Tools for singing voice synthesis and vocal conversion focused on music have greatly improved in both quality and ease of use, leading to an explosion of music with synthetic vocals. This proliferation has made it difficult for listeners to discern human from deepfake and synthetic vocals. While there are robust approaches for detecting synthetic speech and vocal spoofing, identifying synthetic singing voices presents a unique set of challenges. In this paper, we present a new, publicly available dataset of labeled music tracks containing human and synthetic vocals. We evaluate existing synthetic speech detection models using this new dataset. We also introduce a novel ensemble approach that combines high-level speech representations from HuBERT embeddings with a CNN classifier using traditional low-level audio features. Our evaluation confirms this to be an effective approach. We share our results, trained models, and our labeled dataset to encourage future research.

1 Introduction

The proliferation of tools for singing voice synthesis and vocal conversion focused on music have greatly improved in both quality and ease of use, leading to an explosion of music with synthetic vocals. From a listener’s perspective, it can be difficult to discern human from deepfake and synthetic vocals. With implications across the music industry for artists, creators, content providers, rights holders, streaming platforms and listeners, music with synthetic vocals will be in a new category of regulated content: In 2024, the European Union’s Artificial Intelligence Act¹ mandated labeling for AI generated content (other countries may enact similar requirements). With this, there is a growing need for research to find ways to label and detect deepfake and generated content. While there are robust approaches for detecting synthetic speech and vocal spoofing, identifying synthetic singing voices presents a unique set of challenges. As such, we focus on the problem of detecting synthetic vocals in music.

In this paper, we aim to answer three questions: 1. Can solutions built to detect synthetic speech be an effective tool for singing voice deepfake detection without retraining or fine tuning? 2. What input features would be appropriate to solve this problem? 3. Can model architectures successful for other classification tasks be useful? To answer these questions, we present a new, publicly available dataset of labeled music tracks containing human and synthetic vocals gathered from “in the wild” public sources. We evaluate existing synthetic speech detection models using this new dataset. We also

¹<https://artificialintelligenceact.eu/>

introduce a novel ensemble approach that combines high-level speech representations from HuBERT embeddings with a CNN classifier using traditional low-level audio features. Our evaluation confirms this to be an effective approach. We share our results, trained models, and our labeled dataset to encourage future research.

2 Background and Related Work

Advances in generative models for speech synthesis (Arik et al., 2017) and voice conversion (the ability to transform a source speaker’s voice to a target speaker’s voice) (Arik et al., 2018; Qian et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2021; van Niekerk et al., 2022; Ansari et al., 2015) have encouraged researchers to build robust and generalized anti-spoofing techniques to detect synthetic and deepfake speech (Li et al., 2021a; Hua et al., 2021; Li et al., 2021b; Jung et al., 2022; Sun et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2023). Models and tools for singing voice synthesis and singing voice conversion have also seen great improvements (Zhou et al., 2025; Chen et al., 2019; Li et al., 2021c; Liu et al., 2022; Takahashi et al., 2022; Deng et al., 2020). Identifying synthetic or deepfake singing voices presents a unique set of challenges and is a small but growing area of research. SingFake (Zang et al., 2023) presented an initial dataset and baseline models, while the 2024 Singing Voice Deepfake Detection Challenge (Zhang et al., 2024b) brought together a group of research teams employing different approaches. One team leveraged speech foundational ensemble models (Guragain et al., 2024), while another used stochastic local search (SLS) with self-supervised speech model features (XLS-R and WavLM) (Zhang et al., 2024a). Evaluations were conducted against a common dataset (Zang et al., 2024).

3 The Human / AI Repertoire Dataset

3.1 Data Collecting and Labeling

For any singing voice deepfake detection tool to be practical, it must be able to perform well in real world settings. We set out to collect a training and evaluation dataset from public sources that could be representative of a "real world setting" consisting of popular content found on video or streaming sites (the majority of this dataset was sourced from *Youtube*), places where listeners would encounter synthetic or deepfake singing voices. We curated this dataset to be representative of current popular music across genres that could be of primary interest to stakeholders in the music industry. We make this dataset available to add another evaluation tool for this area of research. We believe having a broad range of datasets representing different perspectives will help the overall research in this space.

We collected primarily English language tracks of western popular music, including hip-hop (average duration: 3m 06s) that were self-reported as containing synthetic vocals (these labels were then confirmed with a music industry expert who evaluated both the content and metadata). These tracks constituted our "AI" labeled data. The human labeled, "real" vocal tracks were curated by a music industry expert to be representative of western popular music over the last four decades with a bias towards recency. All the tracks (labeled as "human" or "AI") were restricted to having only one consistent vocalist, and were meant to be representative of popular genres and contain vocals with recording effects commonly used in popular music (autotune, reverb, delay, etc). We collected and labeled 590 tracks with 295 labeled "AI" and 295 labeled as "human". We name this dataset the *Human / AI Repertoire Dataset* (HAIR).

For our models, we used a 81.67% / 10% / 8.33% train/test/tune split. The test set was selected to be representative of current and popular music so that we could understand performance on a subset of music that would be of interest to stakeholders in the music industry, while the train and tune sets were split randomly. The labeled data with original urls can be found in our repository².

3.2 Data Processing

Our data was processed in the following steps:

1. Tracks downloaded as mp3 codec files

²<https://github.com/gabelev/HuBERT-Ensemble-Models-for-Singing-Voice-Deepfake-Detection>

2. Loaded into memory using the Librosa³ Python audio library as mono audio at a 44,100kHz sample rate
3. Vocal stems were separated out using an open source, pre-trained, Python TensorFlow model (Spleeter⁴)
4. Silences were removed from the vocal stems
5. Audio was normalized for volume
6. Audio was cut into 4-second slices and stored as PyTorch tensors (saved to disk using HuggingFace SafeTensors⁵ for the smaller memory footprint)

The decision to extract the isolated vocals instead of predicting on the full track (vocals and music) reduces the classification problem to just singing voice deepfake detection not confounded by other elements in the audio. This allowed us to compare performance with synthetic speech detection models. However, now that there are prompt-based tools to create wholly synthetic generated music and vocals⁶ we may reconsider this step. A Jupyter Notebook with this pre-processing code can be found in our repository along with links to our dataset of already processed torch tensors.

4 Classifiers for Singing Voice Deepfake Detection

Leveraging our dataset (HAIR), we evaluate a range of classifiers for singing voice deepfake detection, experimenting with model architectures, ensemble approaches, and features. We compare the use of both high-level speech representations and low-level audio features. We also compare our singing deepfake models with baseline models that have been previously developed for detecting synthetic speech, to explore whether they generalize from synthetic speech to synthesized singing.

4.1 Baseline models: pre-trained synthetic speech detection models

We selected two models for synthetic speech detection (MCG-Res2Net50 (Li et al., 2021b) and AASIST (Jung et al., 2022)) to act as baselines for our experiments. These models were selected as they represent two very different model architectures, are open-source with available pre-trained model weights, and are trained on a common public dataset for this problem: ASVSpooof2019 LA (Liu et al., 2023). CG-Res2Net50 (Li et al., 2021b) is a Res2Net based model with a channel-wise gated mechanism connection between feature groups. AASIST leverages graph attention networks combining both spectral and temporal features (Jung et al., 2022). Both models have been shown to be effective in detecting synthetic speech.

4.2 Models Trained on HAIR

4.2.1 CNN + spectral features

Because Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) have been successful in image and audio classification tasks, we started with a simple Audio Classification CNN⁷, consisting of 4 convolutional layers with 3x3 kernels.

Input Features

Slicing the extracted vocal audio into 4-second segments, we experimented with different representations of our vocal audio as input features for our models with the following specifications using implementations from torchaudio⁸.

- Mel Spectrograms: 64 mel bands, a hop length of 512, and a window size of 1,024 to calculate the Fast Fourier Transform

³<https://librosa.org/>

⁴<https://github.com/deezer/spleeter>

⁵<https://github.com/huggingface/safetensors>

⁶see: suno.ai, udio.com, riffusion.com

⁷<https://github.com/musikalkemist/pytorchforaudio>

⁸<https://pytorch.org/audio/stable/index.html>

- Mel-frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCCs): number of Mel-Frequency cepstral coefficients to retain at 13, type II discrete cosine transform with an ortho-normal basis, and we construct the Mel Spectrogram for the MFCC with 64 mel bands, a hop length of 512, and an FFT window size of 1,024, with the frame not centered (frame begins at $y[\text{time} * \text{hop length}]$)
- Linear-frequency cepstral Coefficients (LFCC), we set the number of linear frequency cepstral coefficients to retain at 13, type II discrete cosine transform with an ortho-normal basis, and we construct the spectrogram for the LFCC with 64 mel bands, a hop length of 512, and an FFT window size of 1,024, with the frame not centered (frame begins at $y[\text{time} * \text{hop length}]$)

4.2.2 Neural Network with HuBERT Embeddings

We also experimented with extracting activations from a pre-trained HuBERT model (Hsu et al., 2021) – a self-supervised speech representation learning model – to create embeddings that were inputs into Neural Network classifier head. Our intuition is that internal HuBERT representations of voices would encode signal for an effective classifier head.

4.2.3 Ensemble Approach

Finally we experimented with a weighted ensemble of the models trained on our dataset: Neural Network + HuBERT embeddings, CNN + LFCC, and CNN + MFCC.

Table 1: Ensemble model results, predictions correlation and corresponding weights.

Model A	Model B	Model C	Corr. (tune)	Weight A	Weight B	Weight C	EER (tune)	EER (Test)
NN + HuBERT	CNN + LFCC	—	0.269	0.3	0.7	—	0.199	0.311
NN + HuBERT	CNN + MFCC	—	0.334	0.4	0.6	—	0.204	0.315
NN + HuBERT	CNN + Mel	—	0.388	0.3	0.7	—	0.216	0.318
CNN + LFCC	CNN + MFCC	—	0.734	0.5	0.5	—	0.199	0.325
CNN + LFCC	CNN + Mel	—	0.672	0.5	0.5	—	0.211	0.301
CNN + MFCC	CNN + Mel	—	0.731	0.7	0.3	—	0.194	0.331
NN + HuBERT	CNN + MFCC	CNN + LFCC	—	0.33	0.33	0.33	—	0.302

5 Experiment Details

5.1 Number of parameters per model

- CNN with MFCC and LFCC input features: 100,995 parameters
- CNN with Mel Spectrogram as input features: 106,755
- Hubert: 94,888,845. These were pre-trained and not tuned by us. That number does not include the final classifier head; we took the penultimate layer as our embedding.
- Neural Network classifier head for Hubert embeddings: 3,314,789

5.2 Model Initialization

Weights were initialized using the default method in Pytorch: random uniform numbers drawn from

$$(-\sqrt{k}, \sqrt{k}), \text{ where } k = \frac{1}{\#features} \quad (1)$$

5.3 Training Hardware

Models were trained on cloud computing using an instance with 4 vCPUs, 15 GB RAM, and an NVIDIA T4 GPU.

5.4 Evaluation Hardware

Evaluation of the models on our dataset were run in a notebook with a Google Compute Engine A100 GPU back-end with 83.5gb system RAM, 40gb GPU RAM, and 200gb disk.

5.5 Training Time

We found training times to be relatively fast, aside from the (NN + HuBERT), due to the time needed to generate an embedding from the HuBERT pre-trained model’s activations. More effectively batching that part of the algorithm could speed it up significantly.

Table 2: Training Times

Model	Avg Training Time (1 Epoch)
(CNN + MFCC)	20m 58s
(CNN + LFCC)	19m 1s
(CNN + Mel)	21m 41s
(NN + HuBERT)	7h 52m

5.6 Process for Optimal Ensemble Weights

In order to determine the optimal weights for an ensemble approach we:

1. Took the model weights for each model type (CNN + LFCC, CNN + MFCC, CNN + Mel, NN + HuBERT) from the epoch which had the lowest EER on the tuning dataset.
2. For each 2-way combination of models, compute the correlation of their predictions.
3. Find the optimal weights for an ensemble to minimize EER on the tuning dataset:

$$(w * model_a_pred + (1 - w) * model_b_pred) \tag{2}$$

The weight, w , was selected in increments of 0.1 between 0 and 1.

This resulted in weighting the model outputs as follows:

- 30% (NN + HuBERT)
- 70% (CNN + LFCC)

We also looked at a 3-way ensemble between the (NN + HuBERT) and (CNN + LFCC) and (CNN + MFCC) models. To avoid over-fitting to our tune dataset we simply used a $\frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{3}$ weight between the three.

6 Evaluation and Results

To compare results with other work in this research area we use Equal Error Rate (EER) as our evaluation metric along with Receiver Operating Characteristic Area Under the Curve (ROC AUC).

6.1 Baseline results (pretrained synthetic speech detection models)

We report evaluations on 2 existing synthetic speech detection models (MCG-Res2Net50 (Li et al., 2021b) and AASIST (Jung et al., 2022)) against our test dataset to understand how they perform without fine tuning on singing voice deepfake detection. As shown in table 3, these models underperformed compared to those trained specifically for singing voice deepfake detection.

6.2 Evaluation of Models trained on our HAIR dataset

We trained each model architecture on our HAIR dataset. Training was run for up to 20 epochs, saving a model checkpoints periodically. From these, we selected the checkpoint with the lowest EER on our tuning dataset. Each model’s performance peaked before it reached 20 epochs.

We experimented with different combinations of input features and model architectures (results in table 2):

- Neural Network classifier with HuBERT embeddings as input features (NN + HuBERT)

Figure 1: Evaluation Results on HAIR Test Data

Table 3: Evaluation results: models trained on speech and models trains on music vocals

Model	EER (tune)	EER (test)	ROC AUC
MCG-Res2Net50	—	0.530	0.477
AASIST	—	0.450	0.576
1. NN + HuBERT	0.35	0.4	0.64
2. CNN + LFCC	0.21	0.32	0.73
3. CNN + MFCC	0.21	0.34	0.72
4. CNN + Mel	0.22	0.33	0.73
Ensemble of 1, 2, 3.	—	0.302	0.756

- Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) classifier with LFCC input features (CNN + LFCC)
- Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) classifier with MFCC input features (CNN + MFCC)
- Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) classifier with Mel Spectrograms input features (CNN + Mel)
- Ensemble of (NN + HuBERT) and (CNN + LFCC) and (CNN + MFCC)

As we can see in figure 1, this performed slightly better than the (CNN + LFCC)/(NN + HuBERT) ensemble: EER=0.302, ROC AUC=0.756. While the (CNN + LFCC) + (CNN + MFCC) ensemble had marginally lower EER on the tuning dataset, the lower correlation of predictions between (NN + HuBERT) + (CNN + LFCC) suggested that this ensemble could be a more robust predictor.

7 Conclusions

Towards building better tools for singing voice deepfake detection, we presented our labeled dataset (HAIR) and make public our processed data. Our research found that models for singing voice deepfake detection outperform those built and trained on synthetic speech data: synthetic speech detection models do not generalize to singing voice deepfake detection tasks hinting to the unique challenges that singing voices bring to this problem. We found that an ensemble approach worked best: a classifier built with high level speech representations (HuBERT embeddings) coupled with convolutional neural networks with low level audio features (MFCCs and LFCCs). We believe this to

be an exciting and quickly evolving emerging field of research thanks to the growth and availability of high-quality AI Generated music and deepfake vocals along with the proliferation and growing popularity of tools to create this music.

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